

good activity when R=phenyl, *o*-tolyl, *p*-tolyl or *p*-anisyl. In case of 4-thiazolidinones, the compounds containing 5-carboxymethyl are active against *B. megaterium* only.

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Some Halogeno-chalcones

Y. B. VIBHUTE

Department of Chemistry, Yeshwant Mahavidyalaya, Nanded and

M. H. JAGDALE

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur

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CHALCONES have bactericidal¹⁻³, fungicidal⁴, germicidal⁵⁻⁸ activity. Considering these facts various hydroxy halogeno-chalcones have been prepared expecting antimicrobial activity.

α -Naphthaldehyde or 2-methoxy- α -naphthaldehyde, on keeping with hydroxy acetophenones in presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution for 16-24 hrs and subsequent acidification with concentrated hydrochloric acid, yielded the products (Table 1). The products gave positive Wilson test⁹ (yellow colouration) vivid colours on wetting with concentrated sulphuric acid and violet red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. The structures were confirmed by elemental analysis and infrared spectra.

3', 5'-diiodo-2'-hydroxy and 3', 5'-diiodo-4'-hydroxy acetophenones were prepared from 2'-hydroxy-acetophenone and 4'-hydroxy acetophenones respectively by iodination with iodine and iodic acid. 3', 5'-Diiodo-2'-hydroxy and 3', 5'-diiodo-2'-hydroxy-2-methoxy-5',6-benzochalcones were also prepared from 2'-hydroxy and 2'-hydroxy-2-methoxy-5',6-benzochalcones respectively by iodination with iodine and iodic acid.

The purity of all the compounds was checked by tlc.

Infrared spectra of these compounds (Table 2) in Nujol mulls showed the conjugated carbon carbon double bond band at 1600-1550 cm⁻¹ and carbonyl stretching frequency at 1655-1610 cm⁻¹. These assignments are in agreement with those observed by Mahanty *et al*¹⁰ for chalcones.

Experimental

Preparation of 5', 6-benzochalcones: Chalcones were prepared by adding 10% potassium hydroxide (10-20 ml) to an equimolar aldehyde and ketone solution in ethyl alcohol and keeping the reaction mixture at 60° for 16 hrs. The reaction mixture was then diluted with ice cold water. On acidification with conc. hydrochloric acid it gave a yellow product. All the chalcones gave yellow colouration in Wilson test⁹ and pink to dark red colouration with conc. sulfuric acid.

3',5'-Diiodo-2'-hydroxy acetophenone: 2'-Hydroxy acetophenone (0.1639 g) and iodine (2.03 g) were dissolved in ethyl alcohol (50 ml) and heated to about 60°. Iodic acid (0.29 g) in water (2 ml) added with stirring over 0.5 hr. The reaction mixture was then treated with saturated sodium bisulphite solution to decompose the excess of iodine. The separated product was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles, m. p. 127°. Mixed m. p. with an authentic specimen of 3',5'-diiodo-2'-hydroxy acetophenone¹¹ was undepressed, yield 0.35 g (Found: I, 65.93; C₈H₆O₂I₂ requires I, 65.46%).

3',5'-Diiodo-4'-hydroxy acetophenone: 4'-Hydroxy acetophenone (0.163 g) and iodine (2.023 g) in ethanol (70 ml) were heated to 60° and iodic acid (0.29 g) in water (2 ml) was added to it with stirring over 0.5 hr. On working up as before the product separated, which was crystallised from ethyl alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 158°, yield 0.32 g (Found: I, 65.69; C₈H₆O₂I₂ requires I, 65.46%).

Iodination of 2'-hydroxy and 2'-hydroxy-2-methoxy-5', 6-benzochalcones: Benzochalcones (0.01 M) and iodine in excess (0.08 M) were dissolved in ethyl alcohol 50 ml and heated to about 60° and iodic acid (0.3 g) in water added with stirring over 1 hr. The product was obtained on working up as before and crystallised from ethyl alcohol in colourless needles. M. P. and other data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Comp. No.	5 : 6 benzochalcones	m.p.* °C	Crystal appearance	Yield %	Analysis	
					Found	Required
1.	3',5'-diiodo-2'-hydroxy-2-methoxy	218	Pale orange needles ^a	90	I, 45.90 C, 43.41 H, 2.65	I, 45.52 C, 43.01 H, 2.87
2.	3',5'-diiodo-2'-hydroxy	214	Pale orange needles ^t	90	I, 47.91	I, 48.29
3.	3',5'-diiodo-4'-hydroxy	195	Yellow needles ^e	95	I, 47.99	I, 48.35
4.	3',5'-diiodo-4'-hydroxy-2-methoxy	190	Yellow needles ^e	80	I, 45.12	I, 45.52
5.	5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy	152	Yellow needles ^e	80	Cl, 11.12	Cl, 11.54
6.	5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy-2-methoxy	181	Yellow needles ^e	85	Cl, 10.17	Cl, 10.48
7.	3'-chloro-2'-hydroxy	140	Yellow needles ^e	60	Cl, 11.35	Cl, 11.58
8.	3'-chloro-2'-hydroxy-2-methoxy	158	Yellow needles ^a	65	Cl, 10.52	Cl, 10.48
9.	3',5'-dichloro-2'-hydroxy	161	Yellow needles ^a	70	Cl, 23.05	Cl, 20.72
10.	3',5'-dichloro-2'-hydroxy-2-methoxy	202	Yellow needles ^a	70	Cl, 18.93	Cl, 19.03
11.	5'-bromo-2'-hydroxy	138	Yellow needles ^a	95	Br, 21.88	Br, 22.27
12.	5'-bromo-2'-hydroxy-2-methoxy	170	Yellow needles ^a	90	C, 62.09 H, 3.48 Br, 21.12	C, 62.63 H, 3.92 Br, 20.88

* m.p. uncorrected.
a=acetic acid, t=toluene, e=ethyl alcohol.

TABLE 2—INFRARED ABSORPTION DATA AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF THE CHALCONES

Comp. No.*	Antibacterial activity values are mean ± S.E. of 3			Frequency cm ⁻¹ >C=O	Frequency cm ⁻¹ >C=C<
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>X. malva- cearum</i>	<i>X. citri</i>		
1.	Nil	30 ± 1.5	18 ± 1.2	1612	1575
2.	6 ± 0.1	14 ± 1.1	13 ± 1.92	1628	1600
3.	20 ± 0.6	48 ± 1.9	20 ± 0.8	1628	1572
4.	28 ± 0.8	39 ± 0.7	22 ± 0.3	1655	1600
5.	Nil	20 ± 0.6	22 ± 1.3	1638	1572
6.	5 ± 0.8	25 ± 1.5	21 ± 0.9	1644	1585
7.	Nil	23 ± 1.9	31 ± 1.5	1640	1595
8.	Nil	26 ± 1.8	34 ± 1.2	1618	1570
9.	8 ± 0.3	21 ± 0.6	25 ± 1.8	1626	1550
10.	11 ± 1.2	25 ± 1.3	24 ± 0.7	1610	1550
11.	Nil	11 ± 0.5	9 ± 0.2	1628	1555
12.	Nil	20 ± 0.8	17 ± 1.1	1630	1578
Agrimycin-100		45 ± 1.2	38 ± 0.95		
Chloromycetin		48 ± 2.1			

* Compound numbers as in Table 1.

Antibacterial activity : All these (Table 2) compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity following disc diffusion method¹², against three organisms namely *Escherichia coli*, *Xanthomonas malvacearum* and *X. citri*. Paper discs were dipped into the solutions of the different compounds (150 ppm of the substance in 10% ethyl alcohol) and placed at the centres of the bacteria seeded agar plates. The discs were incubated at 30° ± 1° for 24 hrs. The activity was recorded by measuring the diameter of zone of inhibition in mm. Results were standardised against chloromycetin, a commonly used antibiotic for *E. coli* and Agrimycin-100, commonly employed in Plant protection.

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